

STIFFNESS PREDICTION OF THE DOUBLE LAP SHEAR JOINT

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ABSTRACT

Finite element analysis (FEA) is widely used in modeling bonded joints. It is, however, often conducted at the coupon level where the adhesive is modeled, in detail, with a fine mesh. Such an approach is not practical in real world structural analysis. In current FEA structural analysis, adhesive bonds are simplified either as rigid joints, or as spring elements, or substituted by other equivalences. The objective of this study is to assess the accuracy of simplified methods and explore other modeling methods. As a first step, this study is focused on stiffness predictions for the double lap shear (DLS) test.

To facilitate the assessment of different finite element modeling techniques for the stiffness prediction of the DLS test, we analyzed the in-plane stiffness response of a DLS joint. The analytical solution was derived first for a model that considered the shear deformation of the adhesive (Model 1); and then extended to other two simplified models where the adhesive was modeled as a matrix of rigid links (Model 2) or as a line of rigid links (Model 3). The solution for Model 1 agreed well with the experimental results. Using the solution a parameter study was conducted. It showed that the variation in substrate geometries and material properties had a much stronger effect than that of the adhesive properties on the stiffness of the DLS joint. Errors resulting from the simplifications of Models 2 and 3 were estimated. In general, Model 2 overestimated whereas Model 3 underestimated the stiffness of the DLS joints. The magnitude of the error for each model, however, varied with the material system of the joint.

Using the analytical solution as the baseline, we systematically examined several simplified finite element modeling methods for the stiffness prediction of the double lap shear (DLS) test using ABAQUS and LS-DYNA. The simulation results were also compared with the test data of DLS joints of different material systems including composites and aluminum substrates.

Key words: bonded joint, lap shear, stiffness prediction, analytical solution, FEA analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ability to analyze the performance of adhesively bonded structures from coupon test data is essential to the introduction of new materials such as polymeric composites [1] and aluminum [2,3] in vehicle applications. Although Finite element analysis (FEA) is widely used in modeling bonded joints, it is often conducted at the coupon level where the adhesive is modeled, in detail, with a fine mesh. Such an approach is not practical in real world structural analysis.

In current structural analysis procedures, adhesive bonds are simplified either as rigid joints, or as spring elements [1,2], or substituted by other equivalences such as Alcan's jointline element [2,3] and the undercut element method proposed by Beevers et al. [4]. The accuracy of the rigid joint method has not been evaluated. The jointline element approach appears to be more accurate than the rigid links since it is based on testing data of different joint configurations and geometries. A shortcoming of the jointline approach is that a rather extensive database must be developed before analysis. Focusing on stiffness predictions of car bodies with adhesively bonded structures, Beevers et al. [4] investigated various substitution element methods for stiffness analysis of mild steel coach joints (T-peel). They showed that the simple shell-solid model with

undercut and an adjusted adhesive modulus can represent the stiffness of a coach joint. They also demonstrated the method in component structural analysis.

The objective of this study is to assess the accuracy of simplified methods and explore other modeling methods. As a first step, this study is focused on stiffness predictions for the double lap shear (DLS) test. To establish the baseline to be used in the assessment, the analytical solution of the in-plane stiffness of the DLS joint was sought. This paper presents the derivation of the analytical solution and its validation with test results, and examines several simplified finite element models for bonded joints.

2. DOUBLE LAP SHEAR TESTS AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The Composite substrate materials tested in this work are Azdel ®(GE Plastics), a continuous strand mat, glass reinforced polypropylene thermoplastic and a urethane-based, glass reinforced thermoset Structural Reaction Injection Molded (SRIM) composite. DLS test were also conducted with aluminum substrate using Alcan 5754-0.

Three adhesives were used in this investigation: an experimental, 2-part acrylic adhesive provided by Dow Chemical Company, known as LESA (Low Energy Surface Adhesive), which is specially formulated to bond substrates such as polypropylene; a 1-part, experimental epoxy adhesive (Epoxy-I) provided by Sovereign Specialty Chemicals, Industrial Division (formerly SIA Adhesives, Inc.), SIA 654 ETG; and Betamate 4601 epoxy (Epoxy-II) by Dow Chemical. The elastic properties of these materials are summarized in Table I.

Lap shear specimens were prepared with a 12.7 mm overlap or a 25.4 mm overlap. The following material combinations were prepared: Azdel/LESA; SRIM/LESA; SRIM/Epoxy-I; Al/Epoxy-II. The double lap shear specimens were tested under ambient conditions using an Instron Model 1125 test machine at a rate of 2.54 cm/min. A standard Instron clip-on extensometer was used to measure displacement across the joint. The gage length was 50 mm.

3. ANALYSIS OF THE DOUBLE LAP SHEAR TEST

The lap shear test is a basic screening test for adhesively bonded joints. The lap shear test can be performed using either single or double lap shear configurations. The double lap shear is preferred since it eliminates the load eccentricity and, therefore, reduces peel stress in the adhesive as compared with the single lap shear test.

Stress analysis for adhesively bonded single lap shear test has been the subject of numerous studies. Detailed review can be found in literature [5,6]. The equations obtained from stress analysis do not give a direct relation between the load and deflection, i.e. the global stiffness response, of a lap joint. Nevertheless, these equations may be used to generate such relations when needed, as demonstrated by Owens and Lee-Sullivan [7]. To predict the stiffness loss due to adhesive bond fracture of single lap shear joints, Owens and Lee-Sullivan [7,8] developed a stiffness model for single lap joints by summing a series of tension and shear springs where the stress in each spring is calculated using equations from stress analysis. Owens and Lee-Sullivan's work seems to be the only attempt in literature to consider the stiffness of lap joints through analytical solutions.

In this work, an equation for the global stiffness of a DLS subjected to in-plane tensile load is derived through an analytical solution. Figure 1 is a schematic of a DLS specimen. The substrate has dimensions of width, b ; and thickness, t ; with a Young's modulus, E , in the axial (x) direction; adhesive thickness, t_a ; and the adhesive shear modulus, G .

Assume that F is the total axial force acting on the cross-section of the DLS specimen, Δu is the total axial displacement. Figure 1 indicates that Δu has contributions from three segments: 1) the single leg segment; 2) the double leg segment; and 3) the overlap segment.

3.1 Single Leg Segment (length = l_1)

In the single leg segment, the force F_1 acting on the cross section of the single leg equals the total axial force F and the tensile stress is uniform over the length l_1 i.e.,

$$F_1 = F \text{ and } \sigma_1 = \frac{F_1}{A_1} = \frac{F}{bt}$$

The axial displacement of the single leg segment can be derived as

$$\Delta u_1 = \varepsilon_1 l_1, \varepsilon_1 = \frac{\sigma_1}{E} = \frac{F_1}{A_1 E} = \frac{F}{btE}$$

$$\Delta u_1 = \frac{Fl_1}{btE} \quad (1)$$

3.2 Double Leg Segment (length = l_2)

In the double leg segment, the force F_2 acting on the cross section of each individual leg equals half of the total axial force F . The axial displacement of the double leg segment can be derived the same way as for the single leg segment:

$$F_2 = \frac{F}{2}, \varepsilon_2 = \frac{\sigma_2}{E} = \frac{F_2}{A_2 E} = \frac{F}{2btE}, \Delta u_2 = \varepsilon_2 l_2$$

$$\Delta u_2 = \frac{Fl_2}{2bt E} \quad (2)$$

3.3 Overlap Segment (overlap = l_3)

The axial displacement of the overlap segment has contributions from the shear deformation of the adhesive and the tensile deformation of the substrates in the overlap segment.

There are two adhesive layers in a DLS specimen and the axial force F is equally shared by both layers. In a lap shear joint the shear stress in the adhesive peaks at the end of the bonded area. Expressions for stress distributions in lap shear joints have been the topic of a series of elastic analyses [6-14]. In the linear elastic range, however, the total axial displacement due to shear deformation of the adhesive layers would be the same whether it is calculated using an exact stress distribution or the average shear stress in the adhesive. For simplicity, the average shear stress is used:

$$F_3 = \frac{F}{2}, \tau_{ave} = \frac{F_3}{A_3} = \frac{F}{2bl_3} \quad (3)$$

The axial displacement due to shear deformation of the adhesive layers is

$$\Delta u_{3s} = t_a \gamma$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\tau_{ave}}{G} = \frac{F_3}{A_3 G} = \frac{F}{2bl_3 G}$$

$$\Delta u_{3s} = \frac{Ft_a}{2bl_3 G} \quad (4)$$

Next, consider the tensile deformation of the substrates. In the overlap segment the force in the substrate pieces varies from a maximum value, F , to zero from the bonded side to the free end. For simplicity, a linear force distribution is assumed and the average force in single leg is

$$\bar{F}_3 = \frac{F}{2}$$

The displacement due to tensile displacement in single leg under overlap is

$$\Delta u_{3t} = \frac{Fl_3}{2btE} \quad (5)$$

The axial displacement in the double legs of the overlap is smaller than that in the single leg and does not contribute to the net displacement (as long as the thickness of the double leg is equal to, or greater than, one half the thickness of the single leg).

The total axial displacement Δu due to force F is the summation of Eqs. 1, 2, 4 and 5.

$$\Delta u = \Delta u_1 + \Delta u_2 + \Delta u_{3s} + \Delta u_{3t} = \frac{Fl_1}{btE} + \frac{Fl_2}{2btE} + \frac{Ft_a}{2bl_3G} + \frac{Fl_3}{2btE} \quad (6)$$

If $l_1 = l_2$, Eq.6 is simplified into

$$\Delta u = \frac{3Fl_1}{2btE} \left(1 + \frac{t_a E}{3l_1 l_3 G} + \frac{l_3}{3l_1} \right) \quad (7)$$

If $l_1 \neq l_2$, Eq.6 is written as

$$\Delta u = \frac{Fl_1}{btE} \left(1 + \frac{l_2}{2l_1} + \frac{t_a E}{2l_1 l_3 G} + \frac{l_3}{2l_1} \right) \quad (8)$$

For simplicity, the above analysis assumes the DLS is made with substrates of the same material and legs of the same thickness. Similarly, analysis can be performed for DLS with dissimilar materials and different leg thickness.

To verify the analytical solution, stiffness predictions were calculated for Al/Epoxy-II DLS tests of different joint geometries and compared with the test results, as shown in Fig. 2. The slopes of linear portion of these curves gives the stiffness of the joints. The prediction is within the scatter of the test curves. It should be noted that in Figure 2 the linear range of the test curves ends at about 0.05 mm, which is 0.1% of the 50 mm gage length of the extensometer. Scatters in measurement are inevitable in the initial small displacement range.

Using the analytical solution, we can conduct parametric studies to investigate the effect of test parameter variation on the stiffness response of DLS. As an example, Table II presents the calculated percentage changes in DLS stiffness due to 10% variations in specimen geometries (adhesive thickness, substrate thickness, overlap length) or in material properties (Young's modulus of the substrate and the shear modulus of the adhesive) for two Azdel/LESA joint geometries. It shows that 10% variations in substrate material properties and geometries produced about the same percentage change in DLS stiffness whereas 10% variations in adhesive properties and thickness resulted in very little change (0.1% to 0.3%) in DLS stiffness. 10% variation in overlap length resulted in 1% to 2.2% variations in stiffness. The modulus of Azdel material varied between 5-7 GPa and this variation resulted in a significant scatter in the slopes (stiffness) of the DLS test curves, Figure 3. The lower and upper bounds of the scatter is predictable using the analytical solution with $E=5$ GPa and $E=7$ GPa.

3.4 Modeling the Adhesive as a Matrix of Rigid Links

In large component or vehicle structural analysis, the adhesive bond is often modeled by simplified methods such as using common nodes or a matrix of rigid links between bonded substrates. When modeling the adhesive as a matrix of rigid links or common nodes, we need to reconsider the analysis for the overlap segment in section 3.3.

The rigid link model does not allow shear deformation between the legs in the overlap segment and the three legs will deform as one piece. The tensile load is equally shared among the three legs and the tensile stress distribution is uniform along the overlap. The differences in tensile stress variations in the single leg piece and double leg pieces between a matrix of rigid link model and the general model discussed in section 3.3 are compared in Fig.4. The

corresponding effective areas of the substrate pieces in the overlap segment for the two cases are also illustrated.

For a matrix of rigid links model, the displacement due to tensile displacement in the substrate under overlap will be

$$\bar{F}_3 = \frac{F}{3}, \Delta u_{3t} = \frac{Fl_3}{3btE} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\Delta u = \frac{3Fl_1}{2btE} \left(1 + \frac{2l_3}{9l_1}\right) \quad (10)$$

3.5 Modeling the Adhesive as a Line of Rigid Links

The analysis in section 3.4 is for the case when rigid links are defined between every pairs of nodes at the overlap. In structural analysis, adhesive bonds have also been modeled by rigid links along a line of nodes. Using the same practice, we will define rigid links across the width of the coupon along a line through the center point of the overlap. In this case, the tensile load is transferred from single leg to double legs through the rigid links. The differences between this model and the above two models are shown in Figure 4.

For the line rigid model, the deformation over the overlap will be

$$\Delta u_{3t} = \frac{F \frac{l_3}{2}}{btE} + \frac{F \frac{l_3}{2}}{2btE} = \frac{3Fl_3}{4btE} \quad (11)$$

and the total deformation is

$$\Delta u = \frac{3Fl_1}{2btE} \left(1 + \frac{l_3}{2l_1}\right) \quad (12)$$

The errors resulting from using the rigid model or the line rigid model to represent adhesives vary with the joint system and geometries. As an example, Table III lists the error for SRIM/LESA having four different joint geometries and Al/epoxy having two different joint geometries. Table III shows that the two rigid models produced much larger errors in the 25.4 mm overlap joint as compared to the 12.7 mm overlap joint. The rigid model overestimated the stiffness whereas the line rigid model underestimated the stiffness of adhesive bonded joint.

The above results reveal that although the shear deformation of the adhesive layer itself contributes very little to the total displacement of the DLS test, it controls the way the substrate deforms in the overlap segment, as illustrated in Figure 4. Neglecting the shear deformation of the adhesive can lead to significant error in the calculation of the deformation of the overlap segment.

4. SIMPLIFIED FE MODELS

Shell/Solid Model: In this model, the adherent is modeled by shell elements and adhesive is represented by solid elements as shown in Fig.5a. The nodes at the end of double legs are fully constrained and uniform displacement is applied at the nodes at the end of single leg.

Contact Model: In this model, the adherent is modeled by shell elements and the adherents are joined together through tied contact. LS-DYNA allows tiebreak contact and recommends it to be used to represent adhesives [9]. Tiebreak is not allowed in ABAQUS Standard [10].

Line Rigid Model: In this model, the adherent is modeled by shell elements and the adherents are joined at the nodes along the central line of the overlap using rigid links, as shown in Fig.5b.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of FEA with three simplified models were compared with the analytical solutions for the SRIM/Epoxy-I DLS test. Figure 6 plots the results for ABAQUS simulations. It is interesting to see that the three FE models agree with the corresponding analytical solutions for three cases: the shell/solid model agrees with the general analytical solution of Eq.7, the contact model agrees with the analytical solution for rigid model Eq.10 and the line rigid model agrees with the analytical solution for the line of rigid links model of Eq.12. This reveals that the contact definition in ABAQUS is relatively rigid and is equivalent to rigid links between the two surfaces.

Figure 7 plots results for LS-DYNA simulations. As seen, the result of contact model is close to that of shell/solid model and to the prediction of analytical solution Eq.7. This indicates that the contact algorithm in LS-DYNA is close to real world physics. Using LS-DYNA, the line rigid model produced a more compliant joint than predicted by analytical solution of Eq.12. This may be caused by the rotational degree of freedom allowed in constrained-nodal-rigid-body definition in LS-DYNA [11].

The three simplified FE models were also assessed with DLS of other material combinations and the same trends were observed. Based on the results of this study, we recommend using the shell/solid model to represent the bonded joints for ABAQUS structural analysis and the contact model for crashworthiness analysis using LS-DYNA.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The in-plane stiffness response of double lap shear (DLS) joints was analyzed. The analytical solution was derived first for a model (1) considering shear deformation of the adhesive; and then extended to simplified models (2) modeling the adhesive as matrix of rigid links and (3) modeling the adhesive as a line of rigid links. The analytical solution for Model (1) was verified with the test results.

Using the analytical solution a parameter study was conducted. It showed that the variation in substrate geometries and material properties had much stronger effect on the in-plane stiffness response of the DLS joint than that of the adhesive. Errors resulting from the simplifications of Models (2) and (3) were estimated. In general Model (2) overestimated whereas Model (3) underestimated the stiffness response of the DLS joints. The magnitude of the error for each model varied with the material systems of the joint.

Three simplified FE models were examined and the results were compared with the baseline data calculated using the analytical solution and test curves. Based on the results of this study, the shell/solid model recommended for ABAQUS structural analysis and the contact model is recommended for crashworthiness analysis using LS-DYNA.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Table I. Elastic Properties of Adhesive and Adherents

	LESA	Epoxy-I	Epoxy-II	SRIM	AZDEL	Al 5754
Modulus E_1 (GPa)	2.0	3.72	3.97	9.9	6.0±1.0	70.0
Modulus E_2 (GPa)	2.0	3.72	3.97	9.3	6.0±1.0	70.0
Shear Modulus G_{12} (GPa)	0.898	1.314	1.1	3.19	2.1	26.9
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.144	0.34	0.374	0.327	0.3	0.3
Density (g/cc)	1.12			1.49	1.26	2.7

TABLE II. Change In Stiffness Of Azdel/Lesa DLS Due To ±10% Variations In Specimen Geometries Or Material Properties

	Adhesive thickness	Substrate thickness	Overlap length	E modulus of the substrate	Shear modulus of adhesive
Baseline(1.3/12.7)*	1	1	1	1	1
+10%	-0.3%	9.7%	1.2%	9.7%	0.3%
-10%	0.3%	-9.7%	-1.2%	-9.7%	-0.3%
Baseline(0.7/25.4)*	1	1	1	1	1
+10%	-0.1%	9.9%	2.1%	9.9%	0.08%
-10%	0.1%	-9.9%	-2.1%	-9.9%	-0.1%

*(adhesive thickness/overlap length)

Table III. Errors resulting from using rigid or line rigid elements to model the adhesive for DLS estimated using the analytical solutions given in Eq.7, Eq.10 and Eq.12

	SRIM/LESA				Al/epoxy	
Substrate thickness t (mm)	3	3	3	3	2	2
Adhesive thickness t_a (mm)	0.7	0.7	1.3	1.3	0.7	1.3
Overlap length l_3 (mm)	25.4	12.7	12.7	25.4	12.7	25.4
Single (=double) leg length l_1 (mm)	12.3	18.65	18.65	12.3	18.65	12.3
Adhesive shear modulus G (GPa)	0.898	0.898	0.898	0.898	1.31	1.31
Substrate Young's modulus E (GPa)	9.9	9.9	9.9	9.9	70	70
Stiffness (kN/mm) Eq.7 (general)	23.9	21.4	20.9	23.6	95.4	105.0
Stiffness (kN/mm) Eq.10 (rigid link)	28.0	23.4	23.4	28.0	110.4	132.1
Stiffness (kN/mm) Eq.12 (line rigid)	20.1	20.1	20.1	20.1	94.8	94.8
(%) error of rigid link Eq.10	17.4	9.4	11.8	18.9	15.7	25.9
(%) error of line rigid Eq.12	-15.7	-6.0	-3.9	-14.7	-0.64	-9.7

Figure 1. Schematic of a DLS test specimen and the notation for analytical solutions.

Figure 2. Comparison of five DLS test curves (test x) with DLS analysis for Al/Epoxy-II DL specimens with a 12.7 mm overlap and an adhesive thickness of 0.76 mm (left); 25.4 mm overlap and an adhesive thickness of 0.76 mm (right).

Figure 3. Comparison of five DLS test curves (Ax_x) with DLS analysis for Azdel/LESA DLS specimens with a 12.7 mm overlap and an adhesive thickness of 1.3 mm (left) and 25.4 mm overlap and an adhesive thickness of 0.76 mm (right).

Figure 4. Comparison of the effective area of the substrate in the overlap segment of a DLS specimen (upper) and the corresponding tensile stress distribution (lower) in the double leg and single leg pieces when modeled by (a) considering the shear deformation of the adhesive; (b) modeling the adhesive as a matrix of rigid links; (c) modeling the adhesive as a line of rigid links. l_3 =overlap length.

Figure 5. (a) Shell/solid finite element model for a DLS; adherent is modeled with shell elements while the adhesive is represented by solid elements. The boundary conditions are the same as for the solid model. (b) Line of rigid links model for DLS. The adhesive bond is modeled as a line of rigid links (arrow). Note: only a half of the DLS specimen is modeled and a symmetrical boundary condition, $u_3=0$, is imposed.

Figure 6. A comparison of analytical solutions for DLS test for three cases: (1) considering the deformation of adhesive layer, Eq.7; (2) assuming a matrix of rigid links between adherents (all rigid), Eq.10; (3) assuming a line of rigid links between adherents (line rigid), Eq.12. These three cases correspond to the ABAQUS models: adhesive is modeled using (1) solid elements; (2) tied-contact; (3) a line of rigid beam elements.

Figure 7. A comparison of the analytical solutions for DLS test for three cases with three LS-DYNA simulations where the adhesive is modeled using (1) solid elements; (2) surface-to-surface tied-break contact; and (3) a line of constrained nodes (line rigid).